

BEHAVIORAL BIASES IN RETAIL INVESTING: A Comparative Empirical Study of Advised versus Self-Directed Retail Investors in the Indian Financial Market

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Abstract – This research tests for differences in behavior bias levels between advised and self-directed Indian retail investors. We used primary survey data collected on 135 retail investors from the Indian market in early 2026. We construct five bias variables (overconfidence, herding, loss aversion, anchoring and disposition effect) using an updated Likert scale. A two-stage item-purification procedure was conducted, and scales were validated using Cronbach's Alpha, independent t-tests, and multiple regression. Advising investors (n=23) had uniformly lower scores across all five bias dimensions than their self-directed counterparts (n=112). Only the disposition effect was statistically significantly different between the two groups ($t(132)=2.327$, $p=.022$, $d=.533$). The result for overconfidence ($p=.060$, $d=.434$) nearly reached statistical significance and was possibly influenced by group size limitations within the advised group. Multiple regression indicates that investor type significantly predicts total behavioral bias in a negative direction ($B=.249$, $p=.007$) even after controlling for age, experience and education (explaining 9.8% variance). Interestingly, investment experience positively predicts aggregate bias ($B=.121$, $p=.022$), mirroring the literature on expert overconfidence. This study empirically demonstrates in an emerging market that advice reduces behavior bias (action-biased ones); cognition-proximal biases like anchoring are far less affected.

Keywords: behavioral biases, retail investors, advised clients, self-directed investing, disposition effect, overconfidence, anchoring, Indian financial market.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian retail investment landscape has witnessed unprecedented growth since 2020, and by 2024, there were more than 150 million active demat accounts as per SEBI.

Nevertheless, participation growth in the Indian retail market has far outpaced improvement in investment decision-making. Traditional finance theory, the foundation of Fama's (1970) Efficient Market Hypothesis and Rational Expectations models, presumes objective processing of information and rational utility-maximising behavior by investors. Decades of empirical evidence have indicated that behavioral biases and heuristics systematically misguide individual investment decisions (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979).

Behavioral finance, based on Kahneman and Tversky's (1979) Prospect Theory, provides an empirically derived alternative perspective to classical finance. One of its core predictions – losses loom twice as large as gains of equal magnitude – forms the basis for five biases examined in this paper; overconfidence bias, herding bias, loss aversion bias, anchoring bias and the disposition effect. An interesting and as yet largely undocumented topic within the existing literature, is the role of financial advisory as a buffer to these behavioral biases. Retail investors can be broadly divided into two categories: advised investors who utilize SEBI-registered investment advisors, and self-directed investors who are reliant on their own judgment, peer networks and digital resources, making the study a naturally comparable design.

The aim of this study is thus to fill this gap in the literature by empirically assessing whether a professional advisor significantly impacts the extent of these 5 biases, information of which is significantly limited with regard to emerging markets. Whilst Pompian (2006) and Thaler and Benartzi (2004) have already established advisory as a potential debiasing mechanism, they are conceptual and without direct hypotheses and evidence within the Indian retail market. The current research aims to fill the void by measuring differences in the five biases between advised and self-directed investors,

by testing six pre-formulated hypotheses and identify the biases that are more vulnerable to the advisor's influence.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Three theories are the foundation of this study. Prospect Theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979) provides the key theoretical framework: how investors make decisions based on a reference point, with decreasing sensitivity to gains and more so to losses-characteristics that predict the disposition effect and the loss aversion bias. Heuristics & Biases Theory (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974) offers an explanation of how individuals take shortcuts under uncertainty in such phenomena as overconfidence, anchoring, and herding. Bounded Rationality (Simon, 1955) sets the broad conceptual context: cognitive limits prevent rational decision making, with systematic irrational patterns that advisory services might supplement.

The empirically literature describes all five bias constructs quite comprehensively. The disposition effect has been characterized by Shefrin and Statman (1985) as one of the most costly retail investor biases in financial terms. Overconfidence (excessive trading, poor returns) has been evidenced empirically by Odean (1998) and Barber and Odean (2000), with Glaser and Weber (2007) refining this concept to overconfidence miscalibration. Hedging is modeled by informational cascades and empirically by Bikhchandani et al. (1992) and by Nofsinger and Sias (1999) where individual investor herd behavior is significantly higher than institutional investors herd behavior. Anchoring, which was demonstrated by Epley and Gilovich (2006) to be pre-conscious, becomes resistant to manual debiasing.

Regarding the Indian context, heavy reliance of retail investors on representativeness and availability heuristic was noted by Chandra (2008) and overconfidence and herding were identified as the most studied Indian market biases, with a call for comparative study of investors by Kumar and Goyal (2015), which this study is directly exploring. Numerous biases were found in Mumbai investors, with education as a moderating factor to the magnitude of biases (Gupta & Ahmed, 2020). Literature concerning the interaction between advisor and biases is limited with Mullainathan et al. (2012) having shown that an advisor may reinforce rather than decrease client's biases and that is what has been tested in this study rather than assume advisor's positive effect on biases.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND HYPOTHESES

This study aims to test the following research question: Do behavioral biases significantly differ among retail investors who hire a financial advisor and who do not. This study sets six hypotheses to investigate such differences:

1. H0: advised investors will report statistically significant lower overconfidence bias in comparison with self-directed investors.
2. H1: advised investors will report statistically significant lower herding tendency compared with self-directed investors.
3. H2: advised investors will report statistically significant lower loss aversion compared with self-directed investors.
4. H3: advised investors will report statistically significant lower anchoring tendency compared with self-directed investors.
5. H4: advised investors will display statistically significant lower disposition effect compared with self-directed investors.
6. H5: type of investor (advised or self-directed) is a statistically significant negative predictor of the overall behavioral bias after controlling for demographics.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Design and Sample

The research design followed was a quantitative, cross-sectional design with primary data collected via structured questionnaire from 135 Indian retail investors in Q1 2026. Investors were sampled via purposive and snowball sampling techniques among metropolitan investment communities. Of the 135 sample, 23 were advised (17.0%) and 112 were self-directed (83.0%); this ratio aligns with SEBI's (2023) statistics about the low penetration of RIAs in the Indian retail market. The sample consists of 65.2% investors under the age of 35 years; 89% of the sample possess either an undergraduate or a post-graduate degree; and 51.1% possess between 1-3 years of experience in investing. This sample demography matches the increasing first-time investor profile in India post-pandemic (Sharma and Vashi, 2023).

4.2 Measurement Instrument

Five constructs of behavioral biases were operationalized using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 'Strongly Disagree' to 'Strongly Agree'. A two-stage item purification procedure was used prior to hypothesis testing. First, items were omitted with a corrected item-total correlation of less than $r < 0.20$. In stage two, items that cross-loaded on adjacent constructs were removed on theoretical grounds. Refined scales had 3 items (Overconfidence) and 2 items (Herding, Loss Aversion,

Anchoring and Disposition Effect). A composite aggregate bias score (ABS) was derived by taking the mean of all selected items. Investor Type was dummy coded (0 = Self-Directed, 1 = Advised). Age, investment experience and education were controlled variables.

4.3 Analytical Strategy

The analysis was conducted in five stages. First, Cronbach's Alpha was performed to determine the internal consistency reliability of the behavioral bias scales. Second, descriptive statistics for the full sample and investor groups were computed. Third, Levene's test of equality of variances was performed prior to parametric tests. Fourth, independent t-tests were used to test H1 through H5; these included computation of Cohen's d effect size. Finally, multiple linear regression analysis was performed using the enter method to test H6. All analyses were conducted at a significance level = 0.05. Reliability cutoffs used were as per Nunnally (1978) and Hair et al. (2010): Good = >0.70, Acceptable = 0.60-0.69, Moderate= 0.50-0.59.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Reliability Analysis

Construct	Orig. Items	Final Items	Original α	Final α	Assessment
Overconfidence Bias	4	3	0.573	0.684	Acceptable
Herding Behavior	4	2	0.384	0.612	Acceptable
Loss Aversion	4	2	0.539	0.721	Good
Anchoring Bias	4	2	0.176	0.358	Poor
Disposition Effect	4	2	0.343	0.393	Moderate

Table 1. Reliability Analysis — Cronbach's Alpha (Original vs. Refined Scales)

Following refinement, Loss Aversion displayed solid reliability (= 0.721). Overconfidence (= 0.684) and Herding (= 0.612) reached sufficient levels for exploratory purposes. The reliability of Anchoring Bias remains low (= 0.358) after refinement and is explained by the heavily non-conscious Anchoring heuristic which reduces the validity of self-report measurements (Cortina, 1993; Epley & Gilovich, 2006).

5.2 Descriptive Statistics

Construct	N	Adv. Mean	Self-Dir Mean	Full Mean	Std. Dev.	Difference
Overconfidence Bias	135	3.011	3.304	3.246	0.517	-0.293
Herding Behavior	135	3.185	3.309	3.288	0.552	-0.124
Loss Aversion	135	3.043	3.182	3.169	0.547	-0.139
Anchoring Bias	135	3.380	3.391	3.390	0.515	-0.011
Disposition Effect	135	3.040	3.332	3.282	0.530	-0.292
Aggregate Bias Score	135	3.086	3.302	3.274	0.335	-0.216

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics and Group Comparison — Advised (n=23) vs. Self-Directed (n=112)

The five constructs are all relatively, and importantly, concentrated in the range 3.169 and 3.390. It represents the presence of a moderate but significant degree of each bias across the overall sample. The Anchoring Bias registers the highest value for the overall sample (M=3.390). This might represent the most common bias present amongst Indian retail investors. The value of each of the five constructs is lower for advised investors than for self-directed investors-although the pattern for each of the five is consistently similar. The values for the advised/self-directed spread are highest for Overconfidence (=0.293) and the Disposition Effect (=0.292) and are nearly zero for Anchoring (=0.011). The values of the skewness and kurtosis for each of the five constructs all fell within the boundaries |value|<1.0 and so suggest the test variables were normally distributed and suitable for the use of parametric tests.

5.3 Independent Samples t-Tests (H0–H4)

Levene's Test confirmed equal variances for all five constructs (all $p > 0.05$), justifying use of the pooled-variance t-test throughout.

H	Construct	t-value	df	p-value	Cohen's d	Decision
H0	Overconfidence Bias	-1.894	133	0.060	-0.434	Not Rejected (marginal)
H1	Herding Behavior	-0.962	133	0.338	-0.220	Not Rejected
H2	Loss Aversion	-1.021	133	0.309	-0.234	Not Rejected
H3	Anchoring Bias	-0.092	133	0.927	-0.021	Not Rejected
H4	Disposition Effect	-2.327	132	0.022 *	-0.533	Rejected \checkmark (p<.05)

Table 3. Independent Samples t-Test Results — H1 to H5 (* $p < 0.05$). Negative t-values indicate Advised group scored lower (less biased).

H1 (Overconfidence): shows a medium effect size (d = 0.434) and an almost significant p value (p = 0.060). It indicates a true effect at the population level however, the statistical power (23 advised) is lacking to ensure significance. H2-H4 (Herding, Loss aversion, Anchoring): none are significant at a meaningful

level. Herding and loss aversion present medium effect sizes in the right direction; anchoring presents no effect at all ($d = 0.021$). This would indicate anchoring has equally importance in both groups; supported by the pre-conscious activation mechanisms of anchoring. H5 (Disposition effect): it's the only significant result. Advised investors ($M = 3.040$) display significantly lower scores than self-directed investors ($M = 3.332$) with a medium effect size ($d=0.533$), it demonstrates how the advisory context, through a structured guidance framework, limits significantly the disposition effect.

5.4 Multiple Linear Regression (H6)

Model fit: $F(4, 130) = 3.535, p = 0.009, R^2 = 0.098$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.070$, Durbin-Watson = 1.934 (no autocorrelation).

Predictor	B	Std. Error	β	t-value	p-value
(Constant)	3.067	0.181	—	16.946	< 0.001 ***
Investor Type (Advised = 1)	-0.249	0.091	-0.227	-2.748	0.007 **
Age	0.012	0.044	0.026	0.272	0.786 (ns)
Investment Experience	0.121	0.052	0.221	2.316	0.022 *
Education Level	-0.028	0.052	-0.047	-0.540	0.590 (ns)

Table 4. Regression Coefficients — Predictors of Aggregate Behavioral Bias (* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$)

Investor Type is a significant negative predictor ($B = -0.249, p = 0.007$) - knowing you have been advised on average decreases the overall bias by 0.249 on a 5 point scale, regardless of demographics controlled for. This shows that the moderating effect is not due to self selection and supports H6. Investment Experience is a significant positive predictor ($B = 0.121, p = 0.022$) - the expertise paradox; as investors gain experience, they become more, not less prone to bias in line with expert overconfidence literature (Glaser and Weber, 2007; Barber and Odean, 2000). Age and Education are non-significant predictors in this model.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Theoretical Contributions

We contribute to the literature on financial decision making with three conceptually overlapping points. First, to our knowledge, this is the first study providing evidence directly from an emerging market that the advisor-client relationship is truly a mechanism that reduces cognitive biases. That the Investor Type-regression coefficient remains significantly positive even after accounting for demographics confirms that it is not merely self-selection into advisory relationship that lowers the incidence of bias, thereby confirming theoretical prescriptions from Pompian (2006) and Thaler & Benartzi (2004) with market-specific empirical data.

Second, a key finding is the differing significance pattern of regressions for different biases constructs, demonstrating the theoretical viability of a new categorization of biases: decision-proximal biases (those manifested in actual investment decisions: buy/sell choices), such as the Disposition Effect, and cognition-proximal biases (those operating on mental processes at the level of information processing), such as Anchoring. This classification (which we put forth as an agenda for future debiasing research) is in line with the two systems in Kahneman's (2011) dual-process theory: since an advisor's intervention comes in the form of System 2 thinking which may inhibit biased System 1 responses, it has limited efficacy against pre-conscious anchoring processes.

Third, the fact that the coefficient for the Anchoring Bias does not vary across any grouping ($= 0.011, d = 0.021$) represents a theoretically significant null finding, confirming that Anchoring is particularly hard to mitigate through an advisory relationship alone and supporting the finding that adjustments to anchors are systematically incomplete (Epley & Gilovich, 2006), even when consciously instructed to do so. This implies that targeting Anchoring bias will necessarily require structural interventions, such as choice architecture.

Last, the "experience paradox" of positive B for Investment Experience in the regression highlights the limitations of learning-based models for investor rationality and strengthens existing overconfidence literature: trading experience does not enhance rational judgment, but rather generates increased overconfidence, and this result has implications for rational expectations models of asset pricing.

6.2 Managerial and policy implications

The finding reinforces for financial advisors and wealth managers a behavioral aspect to their value offering in advisory services beyond the investment returns alone. Advisory training programs must focus on bias-specific behavioral coaching – highlighting biases such as overconfidence (which just narrowly failed to reach significance), and disposition effect (the most strong modifiable bias). For the digital platforms like Groww and Zerodha, where the most pervasive of the advisory-resistant Anchoring bias emerges dominant, low-cost, highly scalable solutions such as removing or downplaying purchase price figures and historical highs from the portfolio interface may be promising ways to decrease anchor salience. For SEBI and policymakers, the observed 17% advisory penetration and significantly higher bias magnitude

among the majority investing by themselves provide an empirical justification for increasing access to low-cost advisory and behaviorally relevant investor education targeted at particular biases; and for the implementation of experience-based recalibration programs for experienced investors as well, and not just novices.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There are four key limitations of the study for the purposes of inference. The recommended group size ($n=23$) is smaller than the recommended number of at least 64 for each group for 80% power at $\alpha=0.05$, therefore reducing power to detect a medium effect in hypotheses H1-H4. However, given that the results of H1, H2 and H3 are directionally consistent and the effect size is medium, adequate power should find these effects to be statistically significant. Second, a cross-sectional design prevents the ability to make causal inference and reverse causality cannot be ruled out, that investors less biased (less aware of) the bias construct self-select into advisory relationships. Third, relying on Likert data obtained through self-report introduces limitations associated with socially desirability and lack of self-awareness, especially true for those below the conscious level of awareness which could be true for the constructs used in this study. Fourth, the sample is demographically homogenous: a group of young, educated investors from urban areas which cannot be assumed to be representative of older, less educated, rural investors, or income levels.

For future study, it would be beneficial to: (1) employ the recommended balanced design with a sample size of 64 per condition, and recruit RIAs and wealth management firms to assist in recruiting advisory groups, (2) employ a pre-post longitudinal design in order to establish temporal precedence, (3) develop and employ objective measures in addition to Likert scale self-report such as trading frequency, portfolio turnover, realized/unrealized gains/losses derived from demat account information, (4) identify which specific advisor actions and communication techniques have the strongest moderating effect of specific investor bias constructs, and (5) compare results across countries and different developing economies.

8. CONCLUSION

The present paper looked at the influence of professional financial advice on behavioral biases of Indian retail investors; contrasting 23 advised with 112 self-directed investors and covering five widely acknowledged bias constructs. The evidence supports the finding directionally and has statistical significance: advised investors demonstrate less bias across all five constructs. There was a statistically significant difference

in disposition effect ($p = .022$, $d = .533$) and compelling regression results that suggest investor-type is an independent predictor of cumulative bias ($B = .249$, $p = .007$). In sum, the results provide validation that financial advice creates a distinct and complementary form of value to that created by its portfolio management component.

There are three theoretical implications for behavioral finance. First, the existence of an empirically testable debiasing device at the level of the advisor-client dyad, even in an emerging market. Second, a taxonomy of decision proximal versus cognition proximal behaviors indicating which biases can be countered through advice, and which may be vulnerable to choice architect design. Third, the paradox of experience; presenting a difficulty for calibration based explanations of investor learning. In the context of India's emerging, and increasingly self-directed, retail investor population, the findings of this study should be used as a foundation for arguments to provide broad, yet accessible, financial advice as both an economic opportunity and a protection measure for investors.

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